

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING MODERN METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20428155>

Abstract. Nowadays, there is a growing interest in the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical technologies in education, one of the reasons for which to date students are taught only ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies requires them to think independently. teaches to search, analyze and draw conclusions.

Keywords Technology, multimedia, pedagogical technology, information technology, foreign language, IELTS, trends, methods, direct method, language, grammar-translation, audio-visual method, audio lingual method, communicative method, practical skills.

While students are currently taught only ready-made knowledge, the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, and pedagogical technologies in the education system is one of the pressing issues. The use of modern technologies requires students to think independently, research, analyze, and draw conclusions.

The main goal of all reforms in the field of education is to educate spiritually mature people, improve the education system, and implement the teaching process based on new pedagogical and information technologies in line with the requirements of the time. Therefore, today, special attention is paid to the effective use of modern computer and information technologies in the education system. In particular, new methods and requirements for teaching a foreign language in our republic have been developed in accordance with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms have been equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day. The subject of a foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them.

Considering the fact that the position of English as a leading means of international communication in the world is increasingly strengthened and there are no serious tendencies to stop or slow down this process, the problem of using effective methods in this regard is posed. In the modern sense, the educational

process is considered as a process of interaction between teachers and students in order to familiarize students with certain knowledge, skills, abilities and values. Thus, the use of modern information technology tools and methods in the educational process for students in various disciplines allows teachers, first of all, to improve their knowledge and skills in this area, to provide the education system with technical support, and to fully utilize educational and methodological knowledge.

Educational technologies are a set of techniques used in the work of a teacher to achieve the educational goals set in the lesson, the highest efficiency of their application in the minimum possible time.

The characteristics of educational technologies are:

- Efficiency - an indicator of the ability to acquire knowledge and apply it in practice;
- Economy - these are teaching methods that reduce the time for mastering knowledge and developing skills;
- Ergonomics - creating a comfortable learning environment for the teacher and student;
- Motivation - these are tools and methods that encourage students to actively learn.

One of the main ways to improve the quality and efficiency of the education system is to use modern information and communication technologies in the educational process, including multimedia courses, to ensure interactive cooperation between teachers and students, to develop advanced training courses and textbooks, to attract highly qualified multimedia personnel to the educational process.

As is known, today it is difficult to imagine the quality and efficiency of education without modern methods and technologies. The National Personnel Training Program also emphasizes the importance of creating modern educational technologies aimed at solving the problem of mastering the content of education at the stage of developing and implementing a new generation of didactic and informational support for the educational process. In particular, one of such urgent tasks is the development of methods for integrating science and production in the educational process, its implementation in practice, individualization of theoretical and practical training and independent learning, as well as the development and mastering of distance learning technology and its tools, and the acceleration of training students on the basis of new pedagogical methods and distance learning technologies. Today, another important factor in

increasing the effectiveness of education is the use of technical means. This, in turn, increases interest in language learning and the quality of lessons taught, makes students more active in the educational process. If the methods are chosen correctly in the educational process, the desired result can be achieved in a short time. Due to the use of technology in various fields, the whole world has become a global arena, and people can perform all activities very efficiently in a matter of seconds. The introduction of the latest technological innovations in education has also brought more benefits to the education sector, with dramatic changes in students' attitudes towards science and teaching methods. Technology has brought a new dimension to education. In this digital age, there is no place for chalk and blackboards, and digital or smart or interactive boards have been installed instead, thus reducing the teacher's workload and increasing student concentration. In addition, teachers are using digital texts and real materials in their classrooms to stimulate students' interest in the learning point. In recent years, the issue of using modern technologies in the educational process has been increasingly raised. This is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to learning. Our main goal in learning a foreign language using modern technologies is to improve the quality of teaching students in a foreign language, to form and develop their communicative culture, and to effectively use technologies to learn practical skills.

Based on the above, it can be said that when learning a language like English, traditional methods and approaches to language teaching are not interesting for students, and in most cases they do not accept such approaches. However, they are very interested in the latest methods and modern methods of teaching English. The same situation can be observed when teaching English to learners of second language. For this reason, modern English teachers have understood the situation in time and they are mastering new methods in teaching, as well as implementing the latest methods and approaches. There are many traditional methods of teaching foreign languages that are very effective, and currently classical methods are most often used in teaching a foreign language in higher education institutions. In short, modern methods and technologies in the educational process encourage the student to be an active member of the class, think independently, use his mental capabilities, as a result of which long-term memory is preserved. Not only the knowledge of the students, but also their interest, strength, knowledge, teamwork, and freedom of thought increase. As is known, in all types of methods, a problem or question is posed around a specific topic and students are paired up. Each student is given enough time to draw the

right conclusion and students are allowed to share their conclusions with their own voices.

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